

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF POTTERY TERMS IN ENGLISH AND TAJIK LANGUAGES

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Abstract:

The article investigates structural analysis of pottery terms in English and Tajik languages on the basis of morphological method of term formation.

Key words: pottery terms, morphology, syntactic method, compound words, analysis.

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Pottery vocabulary and terminology are a special part of the lexical composition of each language. It has an inseparable connection with many branches of production, a representative of people and human thinking. Words and terms of this lexical stratum, known in the language system as pottery terminology, are reflected in the works of historians and ethnographers who devoted their works to this or that particular craft. The study of compound words in both languages has a long history, and linguists expressed their opinion about this method of word formation in different periods of language development.

So, below all compound terms related to the pottery industry collected in the research process, based on the above-mentioned classification, were grouped as follows: compound terms. The formation of compound terms is considered one of the most productive types of term formation, they are mainly formed from equal roots by different ways and means, expressing different meanings; compound-mixed terms. In the system of Tajik pottery terminology there are a number of complex terms, which are fundamentally different from compound and compound-complex terms. Such compound terms consist of two or more bases and word-forming affixes. With this method, new terms are created from different word combinations and constructions with the help of affixes. Compound terms are formed from two or more bases and a term-forming suffix. These types of compound words are created based on certain patterns such as:

Noun+noun+suffix: kulogari, safolgari, ko'zagari, kosagari are formed from the real nouns kulol, safol, kosa, noun -gar, suffix -i: kulol+gar+i, safol+gar+ӣ, kӯza+gar+ӣ, kosa+gar+ӣ, kosa+gar+ӣ. Kulgarӣ is the profession of a potter or potter: kosagari - shugli kosagar; kosasozi, kosataroshi. With the help of this model, mixed adjectives referring to the potter's wheel were formed: nim+charkh+i. In the system of pottery terminology there is a limited number of terms created on the basis of the mentioned model and expressing the meaning of this or that profession: kum+buz+chi.

Noun+present noun+base of the verb+suffix: This model is used to form compound nouns and adjectives. The compound nouns kosasozi, kosataroshi are formed from the substantives kosa, gil, poshna, gul, the present verb bases soz, tarosh, kun, bur, parto and

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the suffix -i: kosa+soz+i, kosa+tarosh+i, kosa+tarosh+i, gil+kun+i, poshna+bur+i, gul+parto+i, etc. From the nouns ob, otash, choi, non, sang, po'g'an, the present bases of the verbs ho'r, gir, qo'sh, kun, shikan, bar, mol, paz and the suffix -ak the names of household articles are formed: ob+ho'r+ak, otash+gir+ak, choi+qo'sh+ak, non+kun+ak, sang+shikan+ak, ro'g'an+gira+ak, etc.

adverb+noun+suffix: past+nul+ak. In this model, only the word pastno'lak was observed, meaning "a vessel whose spout is located in its lower part".

Noun+noun+suffixes -a and -chi: yak+dast+a, du+go'sh+a, chil+ob+chi. This model is widely used in the formation of compound adjectives.

Adjective + present base of the verb + suffix: zard+paz+i, kabut+gar+i.

In the languages under study, the syntactic mode of term formation is considered to be one of the productive ways or modes of term formation, in the creation of which the components are connected to each other through various syntactic links. Pottery term-word combinations consist of two or more words, components which are linked together by grammatical means and denote complex concepts. Components of the majority of pottery terms, arising from different words, are connected with each other on the basis of subordinating relations, because word-combinations, like words, belong to the group of nominative means of language and reflect the relationship between objects and phenomena, attributes and actions.

Terminology is an integral part of language and includes specific concepts that, along with commonly used words, can express the rise and fall of the culture of each people and nation. In this regard, it can be noted that the lexical composition of the language is in a state of continuous development and evolution, which leads to its enrichment. When unifying and systematizing the terms of this or that field taking into account some criteria related to the issues of terminology and borrowing terms, terminologists need to pay special attention to the peculiarities of this widely used language unit. In our opinion, the establishment and definition of uniform requirements to terms by scientists and linguists is not quite correct, because the only feature that distinguishes a word of general use from a term is its use in a particular field. One of the main features of a term is its use in a specific field and comprehensibility for specialists in this field. One of the distinctive features of pottery terminology is its practical and meaningful connection with other fields such as chemistry and mineralogy, culture and crafts. In addition to the above notions, it should be noted that the system of pottery terminology of the above languages represents not only simple, derivative and complex terms, but is also saturated with numerous terms-phrases. In the system of pottery terminology of Tajik and English languages there are some terms that epitomize the daily activities of pottery specialists. Tajik and English pottery terms are the product of the art of professional potters. This high art continues up to the present time, is in the stage of development and has become one of the most important decorative and artistic arts.

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